

INTERPRETATION OF LINGUISTIC EXPRESSIONS OF PERSONAL FEELINGS

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Language acquires a social essence as the most important means of communication between people. It is also closely related to other social phenomena. Therefore, the language is related to a number of sciences, such as philosophy, history, ethnography, sociology, psychology, ethics, which study issues such as the worldview, past, culture, and psyche of the people. As a result of this relationship, a number of intermediate directions - mentalinguistics, ethnolinguistics, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics, gender linguistics, neurolinguistics, etc. Today, many research works are being carried out in Uzbek and world linguistics in these areas. Personal emotions can be studied within the framework of newly formed areas of linguistics. At first, it is very difficult to understand the meaning of the concepts of feelings and emotions. [2, 256]

ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the aspects of connection with human language of new trends in linguistics, psycholinguistics, neurolinguistics, sociolinguistics. Personal feelings are interpreted from a linguistic point of view. In particular, the verbal expression of the speech activity of the characters in the text is studied.

Methods

Every person on earth has the ability to feel certain feelings (emotions) and express them. Even a newborn baby is born with certain emotions (feelings expressed by facial expressions). Emotion is a mental process, a human response to the environment. The word "emotion" is derived from the Latin word "emoveo", which means "to be touched", "to be excited". Emotions are a magnet that attracts people to people, a means of mutual understanding and explanation, unique to humanity. Some of the emotions are positive, some are negative, and each one has a different effect on the person. Experts say that emotions also have the property of moving from person to person. Have you ever noticed that most of the people around a person who is always smiling and cheerful by nature have the

same personality. Even if you talk to a cheerful person for just 10 minutes, you will feel a sense of relief. You will be happy with yourself, your mood will rise. So, try to be in the conversation of more cheerful people. [5, 124]

Results

This begs the question, what is the relationship between language and emotion? In the process of interpreting the linguistic representations of human emotions, semantics uses the interdisciplinary fields of the relationship between language and emotion, development, perception of emotions, experience and regulation of emotions, and the linguistic interpretation of the nervous system.

Recent decades have seen an explosion of interdisciplinary research on language and emotion in modern linguistics. For example, linguistic research shows that almost all aspects of human speech, including prosody, phonetics, semantics, grammar, speech, and conversation, are directly related to a person's language and emotions. Computational tools applied to natural human language reveal meanings that predict outcomes ranging from health and well-being to political behavior. Anthropological and linguistic studies show differences in the meaning of emotion words around the world, which can contribute to the development of cross-cultural studies of emotional experiences and emotional expressions, and have implications for intercultural communication and diplomacy. Research in developmental psychology and linguistics suggests that caregiver use of emotion words in conversation with infants helps build emotional understanding and self-regulation later in childhood. Psychological,

physiological, and neuroscience research in adults shows that exposure to emotion words alters emotion perception, self-reported emotion, emotion-related physiology, and brain activity and emotion regulation. Therefore, the ability to accurately describe a person's emotional state determines physical, mental and speech health. [8, 56]

Discussion

Perhaps one of the most important questions about the relationship between language and emotion revolves around the information that language conveys about emotion. Spoken language represents experiences, so the study of language can shed light on the nature of emotions. In fact, language conveys emotions through almost all aspects. The most interesting of these aspects is the ability to use the structure of spoken language to ask questions about how people understand emotion concepts and concepts in general. [4, 89]

It may be that accessing emotion labels allows a person to conceptualize their affective state in a discrete and context-appropriate manner and that doing so confers benefits for well-being. Indeed, an abundance of findings shows that individuals who use emotion labels in a discrete and specific manner experience less psychopathology, experience better outcomes following, and engage in less interpersonal aggression. Moreover, individuals who are high in granularity exhibit brain electrophysiology associated with greater semantic retrieval and cognitive control during emotional experiences and use more specific and effective emotion regulation strategies during intense instances of negative emotion.

There are people whose behavior is always demonstrative, he likes to perform all actions demonstratively. He communicates quickly and easily with others, he is active and active. He will be a master of tricks and tricks, prone to lying, an inventor and dreamer, exaggerating his personality. Praiseworthy and arrogant, this person takes risks in any work, strives to lead, to be in the attention of those around him. He quickly gets along with people, quickly adapts to any situation, if his actions are not recognized or ignored by those around him, his mood is quickly broken and he changes the conversation in another direction. At such times, he tries to create scandalous situations in his favor, and he succeeds. [7, 16]

Of course, the study of the relationship between language and emotions draws on

linguistics, anthropology, sociology, cross-cultural psychology, and other social sciences that use ethnography and cross-cultural comparisons to understand cross-linguistic differences and similarities in emotions. Classical studies of the 19th and 20th centuries were able to demonstrate cross-cultural differences and similarities in emotion concepts. Similarly, qualitative comparisons between languages illuminate both variation and underlying commonalities in the semantic meaning of emotion concepts in lexicons. [9, 6]

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that language not only changes the perception of emotions on the faces of others, but also controls how a person experiences and regulates emotions in his own body.

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